

An overview of Customer satisfaction towards digital Marketing in Gorakhpur Region

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Abstract— The term digital marketing is used for targeted, measurable, and interactive marketing of products or services by using various digital technologies to enhance the reachability at consumer doorsteps. The key objective of this activity is to promote the product or service and at the same time to work on the trend image of the company and with the help of that brand equity can be created in the marketplace. It will help to build increasingly prospective buyers and would be beneficial to increase the sale of goods and services by practicing numerous types of digital marketing techniques that are available in the marketplace. Digital Marketing is the Art and Science of selling products and services over digital networks, such as the internet and cellular phone networks. Digital Marketing is becoming a hot topic in every business sector, gradually plays a truly important role in any company's multi-channel marketing strategy.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Customer Satisfaction, Online Marketing, E-commerce.

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital marketing also known as online marketing, is the promotion of brands using the digital communication to connect with inherent customers. This includes not only email, web-based advertising and social media, but also text and multimedia messages as marketing channels. Any marketing that uses electronic tools and can be used by marketing experts to deliver a promotional message and measure its impact through your customer journey. In practice, digital marketing generally refers to marketing campaigns that are visible on a computer, phone, tablet, or other device. This can take many forms including online video, display advertising, search engine marketing, paid social advertising and social media posts. According to Deloitte, 72% of marketers report that the role of marketing has increased in importance during pandemic years.

Digital marketing has become a powerful tool to communicate with new and existing customers, as consumer behaviour has changed a lot over the last 18 months. Due to various restrictions on our daily lives, people have been forced to live differently and as a result, they are shopping and spending their time in different ways.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review literature of is to collect relevant, timely research on your chosen topic, and synthesize it into a cohesive summary of existing knowledge in the field. This then prepares you for making your own argument on that topic, or for conducting your own original research. Afrina Yasmin et al. (2015) His article states that marketers are facing new challenges and opportunities in this digital age. This article focuses on the importance of digital marketing for both marketers and consumers.

Rajiv Kaushik (2016) in his article digital marketing is rising in India with fast pace. Many Indian companies are using digital marketing for competitive advantage. Success of marketing campaign cannot be solely achieved by digital marketing only. Rather for success of any marketing campaign it should fully harness the capabilities of various marketing techniques available within both the traditional and modern marketing. Rekha Dahiya (2017) The impact of digital marketing communication on product categories such as books, music, fashion accessories, clothing, banking and online gaming etc. has been well researched by researchers; But despite being one of the biggest digital spenders, the automobile industry has suffered from a lack of academic study, especially in India. The objective of the present study is to understand the impact of digital marketing communication on the consumer buying decision process in the Indian passenger car market. A mixed method was adopted for the study.

M. Shirisha (2018) - The marketing states that Digital is the fastest e-commerce solution available. In this marketing strategy we can buy or sell fast. You can reach maximum audience. With the help of digital marketing, the customer and you can do this faster. It indeed plays an important role in the modern commerce system. This system makes our business faster and more accurate. Digital marketing is far more cost-effective than traditional online marketing methods. In this paper an attempt has been made to highlight the importance of digital marketing in the new era. Rekha Dahiya (2017) The impact of digital marketing communication on product categories such as books, music, fashion accessories, clothing, banking and online gaming etc. has been well researched by researchers; But despite being one of the biggest digital spenders, the automobile industry has suffered from a lack of academic study, especially in India. The objective of the present study is to understand the impact of digital marketing communication on the consumer buying decision process in the Indian passenger car market. A mixed method was adopted for the study.

Madhu Bala (2018) This paper presents views on some current and future trends in marketing, In this study, we acknowledged that businesses can really benefit from digital marketing such as Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Search Engine Marketing (SEM), Content marketing, influencer marketing, content automation, e-commerce marketing, campaign marketing, and social media marketing, social media optimization, e-mail direct marketing, display advertising, e-books, optical discs and are becoming more common in our growing technology.

III. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

1. To find trends in digital marketing in India.
2. To find review of satisfaction for a digital marketing.
3. To analysis to evaluate satisfaction for a digital marketing.

IV. AREA OF THE STUDY

The study would be a youngster-based study. It will cover the all the young adults living in and around in Gorakhpur Region.

V. HYPOTHESIS

NULL HYPOTHESIS

The means for all groups are the same [equal]

$$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_4 = \dots = \mu_n$$

ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS

The means are different for at least one pair of groups.

$$H_1: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2 \neq \mu_3 \neq \mu_4 = \dots = \mu_n$$

VI. METHODOLOGY ADOPTED

Primary Sources-The primary data has been collected by means of questions and interview method.

Secondary Sources-The secondary data have been collected from various public sources such as Books, Journal, Annual report and Magazines, Newspaper and various websites etc.

Sample design and Sample size-In this study research determine the sample size of 237 customers is chosen by following the technique of simple random sampling. The primary data was collected by using questionnaires.

Statistical tools applied: For the analysis and interpretation of data wherever necessary the simple and primary statistical measures and techniques such as calculation of simple Average Mean, Percentage, Standard Deviation, Variance, and F, test has been applied.

VII. DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

PART-A (DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILES)

I. GENDER

Table -1

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	83	35
Female	154	65
Total	237	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference -From the above table it is inferred that 35% of respondents are male and 65% are female.

II .AGE

Table -2

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-30	234	98.7
30-40	2	0.7
40-50	1	0.4
Above 50	0	0
Total	237	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference- From the above table it is inferred that 98.7% of respondents come under the category of 20-30 years, 0.7% of respondents fall under 30-40 years, 0.4% of respondents come under the category of 40-50 years and 0% of respondents come under the category of above 50 years.

III. MARITAL STATUS

Table -3

Marital status	Frequency	percentages
Married	6	2.5
Unmarried	231	97.5
Total	237	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference-From the above table it is inferred that 2.5% respondents are married and 97.5% are unmarried.

IV. OCCUPATION

Table -4

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Students	228	96.2
Salaried	4	1.7
Professional	1	0.04
Business	4	1.7
Total	237	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference -From the above table it is inferred that 96.2% of respondents are students, 1.7% of respondents are salaried, 0.04% of respondents are professional, and 1.7% of respondents are business.

V. INCOME (P.M.)

Table -5

Income	Frequency	Percentage
0-20,000	198	83.5
20,000-35,000	14	5.9

35,000-45,000	15	6.3
45,000-55,000	7	3
Above 55,000	3	1.3
Total	237	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference- From the above table it is inferred that 83.5% of respondents fall under 0-20,000, 5.9% of respondents fall under 20,000-35,000, 6.3% of respondents fall under 35,000-45,000, 3% of respondents fall under 45,000-55,000, And 1.3% of respondents come under the category of above 55,000 of per month income.

PART B

VIII. TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS

Table 6

Reasons to opt Digital Marketing by Customers

Serial No.	Reasons	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Digital marketing full aware of customers.	28	12%
2.	Do you feel it essential to safe doing digital marketing?	26	11%
3.	All information is clear through digital marketing.	31	13%
4.	Digital marketing guidelines is very easy.	28	12%
5.	Digital marketing payment mode are easy to access.	21	9%
6.	Digital marketing system is easy process.	24	10%
7.	Digital marketing system for delivery status and order summary.	19	8%
8.	Customers satisfied with return policies.	17	7%
9.	Customers fully satisfied with digital marketing.	43	18%
	Total	237	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 7

Reasons vs. level of satisfaction

Serial No.	Reasons	SA	A	N	DA	SDA
1.	Digital marketing full aware of Customers.	55 (23.2%)	127 (53.6%)	36 (15.2%)	15 (6.3%)	4 (1.7%)

2.	Do you feel if essential to safe doing digital marketing.	40 (16.9%)	176 (74.3%)	0 (0%)	20 (18.4%)	1 (0.4%)
3.	All information is clear through digital marketing.	39 (16.5%)	130 (54.9%)	54 (22.8%)	13 (5.5%)	1 (0.4%)
4.	Digital marketing guidelines is very easy.	35 (14.8%)	122 (51.5%)	61 (25.7%)	18 (7.6%)	1 (0.4%)
5.	Digital marketing payment mode are easy to access.	56 (23.6%)	140 (59.1%)	26 (11%)	14 (5.9%)	1 (0.4%)
6.	Digital marketing system is easy process.	49 (20.7%)	147 (62%)	34 (14.31%)	7 (3%)	0 (0%)
7.	Digital marketing system for delivery status and order summary.	53 (22.4%)	134 (56.5%)	37 (15.6%)	12 (5.1%)	1 (0.4%)
8.	Customers satisfied with return policies.	46 (19.5%)	123 (52.1%)	47 (19.9%)	20 (18.5%)	0 (0%)
9.	Customers fully satisfied with digital marketing.	42	120	60	14	1 (0.4%)

Source: Primary Data

Table 8

Calculation of Mean

Sr. no./ No. of questions	Treatment / Likert scale (X)				
	1	2	3	4	5
1	55	127	36	15	4
2	40	176	0	20	1
3	39	130	54	13	1
4	35	122	61	18	1
5	56	140	26	14	1
6	49	147	34	7	0
7	53	134	37	12	1
8	46	123	47	20	0
9	42	120	60	14	1
Total (N)=9	415	1219	355	133	10
Mean (X)	46	135	39	15	1

Note: - Combined mean (\bar{X}_c) =
$$\frac{\bar{x}_1 + \bar{x}_2 + \bar{x}_3 + \bar{x}_4 + \bar{x}_5}{N}$$

$$= \frac{46 + 135 + 39 + 15 + 1}{5}$$

$$= 47$$

Calculation of Variable between Samples

Sum of Deviation Square=

$$N_1 (\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_c)^2 + N_2 (\bar{X}_2 - \bar{X}_c)^2 + N_3 (\bar{X}_3 - \bar{X}_c)^2 + N_4 (\bar{X}_4 - \bar{X}_c)^2 + N_5 (\bar{X}_5 - \bar{X}_c)^2$$

$$= 9(46-47)^2 + 9(135-47)^2 + 9(39-47)^2 + 9(15-47)^2 + 9(1-47)^2$$

$$= 9(-1)^2 + 9(88)^2 + 9(-8)^2 + 9(-32)^2 + 9(-46)^2$$

$$= 98,541$$

Mean of the Sum Square (MSS) = $\frac{\sum [nk(\bar{X}_k - \bar{X}_c)]^2}{df} = SS$

$$df = \frac{\text{Sum of deviation square}}{\text{degree of freedom}}$$

$$= \frac{98,541}{4}$$

$$= 24,635$$

*d.f. = N-1

$$= 5-1 = 4$$

Table 9

Calculation of Variance within sample

s. no/no. of questions	Treatment / 5- point Linkert scale														
	X1	(X1- \bar{X}_1)	(X1- \bar{X}_1) ²	X2	(X2- \bar{X}_2)	(X2- \bar{X}_2) ²	X3	(X3- \bar{X}_3)	(X3- \bar{X}_3) ²	X4	(X4- \bar{X}_4)	(X4- \bar{X}_4) ²	X5	(X5- \bar{X}_5)	(X5- \bar{X}_5) ²
1	55	(55-46) =9	81	127	(127-135) = -8	64	36	(36-39) = -3	9	15	(15-15) = 0	0	4	(4-1) = 3	9
2	40	(40-46) = -6	36	176	(176-135) = 41	1,681	0	(0-39) = -39	1,521	20	(20-15) = 5	25	1	(1-1) = 0	0
3	39	(39-46) = -7	49	130	(130-135) = 5	25	54	(54-39) = 15	225	13	(13-15) = -2	4	1	(1-1) = 0	0

4	35	(35-46) = -11	121	122	(122-135) = -13	169	61	(61-39) =22	484	18	(18-15) = 3	9	1	(1-1) =0	0
5	56	(56-46) =10	100	140	(140-135) = 5	25	26	(26-39) = -13	169	14	(14-15) = -1	1	1	(1-1) = 0	0
6	49	(49-46) =3	9	147	(147-135) =12	114	34	(34-39) = -5	25	7	(7-15) = -8	64	0	(0-1) = 1	1
7	53	(53-46) = 7	49	134	(134-135) = -1	1	37	(37-39) = -2	4	12	(12-15) = -3	9	1	(1-1) = 0	0
8	46	(46-46) =0	0	123	(123-135) = -12	144	47	(47-39) = 8	64	20	(20-15) = 5	25	0	(0-1) = 1	1
9	42	(42-46) = -4	16	120	(120-135) = -15	225	60	(60-39) =21	441	14	(14-15) = -1	1	1	(1-1) =0	0
			461			2,448			2,942			138			11

* Sum of Square Of Deviation = 461+2448+2942+138+11

=6000

$$\text{Variation within sample} = \frac{\sum X - X^2}{N - K}$$

$$= \frac{6,000}{40}$$

$$= 150$$

df₂ = V₂ = N - K

=45-5 =40

Variance between sample

One Way Anova [F- Test] = $\frac{\text{Variance between sample}}{\text{Variance within sample}}$

= 24635

=164

= $F > 2.21$

From the table 9, Tabulated value of F Ratio (F-Test) for 237 df at 5% level of significance at tabulated value is 2.21. Since Calculated Value is much greater than the tabulated value. It is highly significant hence we rejected the Null hypothesis and Conclude that customers satisfied for digital Marketing in India.

IX. SUGGESTIONS

1. Since convenience is the major factor to go digital, the e-retailers must ensure that digital process through sites must be made simple and cost effective.
2. The E-Business people can introduce third party insurance to gain more trust.
3. Accuracy in delivery should not be delayed.
4. Safety measures can be taken to avoid fraud websites

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